

Implementing Early Mobilization in the Intensive Care Unit

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Background

- Early mobility (EM) is vital for patients in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU)
- Prolonged bedrest and immobility can result in multiple complications
- Benefits of EM in the ICU:
 - Can reduce incidence of ICU-Acquired Weakness
 - Can decrease number of ventilator days
 - Can shorten ICU length of stay

Purpose

- To modify the existing MICU progressive mobility protocol
- Implement the modified EM protocol using evidence-based practices
- Evaluate the EM protocol to improve the health outcomes of critically ill patients in the medical intensive care unit (MICU)

Methods

- Quality Improvement Project
- Design: Model for Improvement Framework and PDSA cycle
- Setting: 20-bed medical ICU at a Level I trauma hospital
- Sample: ICU nurses

Measures

- Outcome Measures**
- Average Length of Stay (LOS)
 - Average Ventilatory Days
 - Highest Level of Mobility
- Process Measures**
- Initiation of Mobility
 - Barriers to Mobility
- Balancing Measures**
- Number of Adverse Events

Conceptual Framework

Results

Results

Discussion

- EM education started 02/09/2021 and ended 02/16/2021
- Average LOS in MICU: 6.9 days
- Average Ventilator Days: 10 days
- Only 7% of patients were mobilized during EM education
- Patient barriers to EM:
 - Hemodynamically unstable
 - Presence of line/tubes
 - Sedated
 - Paralyzed
 - Need to be manually prone
- Other barriers:
 - Limited time
 - Limited resources

Limitations

- Imposed restrictions due to COVID-19 pandemic limited activities to critical operations only
- Surge of COVID-19 patients in MICU during planned EM implementation resulted in shortage of nursing staff to assist in EM activities

Conclusion

- In the absence of a pandemic, full implementation of EM protocol can be accomplished
- Incorporating EM into the daily care of ICU patients is feasible with full support of the organization
- A multidisciplinary EM team is critical to the success of EM implementation
- Address barriers to performing EM activities
- Adopt a standardized EM protocol for the ICU